

TABLE 1— R_f VALUES OF IMINES IN BENZENE-ETHYLACETATE (95 : 5)

Sl. No.	Substituent in C-phenyl ring	Substituent in N-phenyl ring	Colour with spraying reagent	R_f
1.	H	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	Gray	0.22
2.	H	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	Light pink	0.23
3.	H	<i>p</i> -OH ₂	Yellow	0.27
4.	H	H	Blue	0.28
5.	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	Yellow	0.31
6.	H	<i>p</i> -Br	Brown	0.41
7.	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	Light brown	0.46
8.	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	Violet	0.20
9.	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	Violet	0.21
10.	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	Light orange	0.36
11.	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	<i>p</i> -OH ₂	Yellow	0.39
12.	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	H	Yellowish green	0.41
13.	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	<i>p</i> -Br	Yellow	0.46
14.	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	<i>p</i> -Cl	Light yellow	0.48
15.	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	Violet	0.27
16.	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	Violet	0.27
17.	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -OH ₂	Light brown	0.39
18.	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	Blue	0.42
19.	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	Yellow	0.44
20.	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br	Yellow	0.87
21.	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	Light yellow	0.90

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Benzohydroxamic Acid as an Indicator in the Titrimetric Determination of

Alkali-Earth Metals

R. D. ROSHANIA and Y. K. AGRAWAL

Pharmacy Department, Faculty of Technology and Engineering, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 001

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HYDROXAMIC acids are widely used as chelating agents for metals¹⁻³. They form coloured complexes with vanadium, titanium, molybdenum, etc⁴⁻⁵. Complexation and gravimetric estimation of the alkali earth metals with hydroxamic acids are reported but they do not give any colour⁶⁻⁸ and the hydroxamic acids have not so far been used as an indicator for the determination of alkali earth metals. In the present investigation, benzohydroxamic acid (BHA) has been used as an indicator for direct titrimetric determination of beryllium, magnesium and calcium. These are determined in presence of each other and several other metal ions.

It is well known that EDTA forms strong complexes with beryllium, magnesium, calcium and iron(III). The fact that iron(III) forms violet

coloured stable complexes with hydroxamic acids has been utilized for titrimetric determination of alkali earth ions. At first the alkali earth ions are complexed with excess EDTA, the excess EDTA is titrated with iron(III) and the excess iron(III) is immediately indicated by the formation of violet reddish brown colour with BHA. Hence, the equivalent amount of metal ion can be determined by back calculation.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of B.D.H., AnalaR or E. Merck, G.R. grades unless otherwise stated.

Metal ion solutions: Standard solutions of beryllium as BeSO₄.4H₂O, magnesium as MgSO₄.7H₂O and calcium as CaNO₃ were prepared by dissolving the requisite amount in distilled water and standardized volumetrically⁹. Standard 0.01 M iron(III) solution was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of ferric ammonium sulphate and standardized volumetrically⁹.

EDTA: Standard 0.01 M EDTA disodium solution was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of disodium EDTA (G.R., E. Merck).

Benzohydroxamic acid: Benzohydroxamic acid was synthesized as described by Agrawal *et al*¹⁰ and directly used as indicator for the titrimetric determination of the alkali earth (Be, Mg and Ca).

Procedure:

In a 250 ml conical flask an aliquot of metal ion solution is transferred and an excess of EDTA (two times the required amount) is added. It is heated upto boiling. After cooling, the pH is adjusted for each metal, and 0.1 g benzohydroxamic acid is added as indicator. It is titrated against standard iron(III) solution to a violet brown red end point.

Results and Discussion

Beryllium:

Beryllium (0.1-5.0 mg) is mixed with standard EDTA solution and titrated in acidic media (0.5-0.8 M HCl) in presence of KCl solution (10 ml of 5%). The end point is indicated by a change from light yellow to red brown colour. The results are shown in Table 1.

Effect of diverse ions: Beryllium could be easily titrated in presence of Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺ and Ba²⁺ in acidic media since these metals form the complexes in alkaline media. Beryllium could be titrated in presence of Cd²⁺, Ti⁴⁺, Ni²⁺, Hg²⁺, UO₂²⁺, Ce⁴⁺, Mn²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Al³⁺ with the addition of tartaric acid and tartrate.

Magnesium:

Magnesium (0.1-5.0 mg) is mixed with standard EDTA solution, the pH is adjusted to 9-10 with ammonium hydroxide (0.1 M) and ammonium chloride (0.1 M) and titrated with standard iron(III) using benzohydroxamic acid as an indicator. The

TABLE I—TITRIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF BERYLLIUM, MAGNESIUM AND CALCIUM WITH BENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID AS INDICATOR

Amount of alkali metal taken mg	Beryllium			Magnesium			Calcium		
	Found mg	Error	SD	Found mg	Error	SD	Found mg	Error	SD
0.25	0.28	+0.02	±0.08	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.50	0.50	+0.00	±0.01	0.50	0.00	±0.01	0.47	+0.08	±0.04
0.75	0.76	-0.01	±0.02	—	—	—	0.77	-0.02	±0.03
1.00	0.98	+0.02	±0.02	—	—	—	0.98	+0.02	±0.02
1.20	—	—	—	1.20	0.00	±0.01	—	—	—
2.00	—	—	—	—	—	—	2.01	-0.01	±0.01
2.25	—	—	—	2.24	-0.01	±0.02	2.25	0.00	±0.01
2.50	2.52	-0.02	±0.02	—	—	—	—	—	—
3.00	—	—	—	—	—	—	2.98	+0.02	±0.02
3.36	—	—	—	3.35	+0.01	±0.02	—	—	—
4.00	—	—	—	3.98	+0.02	±0.03	4.02	-0.02	±0.03
4.50	—	—	—	4.51	-0.01	±0.02	—	—	—
5.00	5.00	0.00	±0.02	—	—	—	5.01	-0.01	±0.02
Effective concentration range (mg)	0.10-20			0.10-25			0.10-25		

colour change is yellow to red. The results are shown in Table I.

Magnesium could not be determined quantitatively beyond this pH range.

Effect of diverse ions: Magnesium could be easily titrated in presence of Be^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} at pH 9-10. In presence of tartrate and tartaric acid magnesium could be titrated from Cd^{2+} , Ti^{4+} , Ni^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , Ce^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Al^{3+} .

Calcium interferes in the determination of magnesium and this can be masked with oxalic acid. 2.5-3.0 times the theoretically calculated amount of oxalic acid is required to mask calcium.

Calcium:

Calcium (0.1-0.5 mg) is mixed with standard EDTA solution, the pH is adjusted to 9-10 with ammonium hydroxide (0.1 M) and ammonium chloride (0.1 M) and titrated with standard iron(III) solution using benzohydroxamic acid as indicator. The colour change is yellow to red. The results are shown in Table I.

Calcium could not be determined quantitatively beyond this range.

Effect of the diverse ions: Results are the same as those for magnesium.

Magnesium interferes in the determination of calcium which can be masked with double the amount of iron(III).

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N-Hydroxy-N-p-Chlorophenyl-N'-(2,3-Dimethylphenyl-p-toluidine Hydrochloride—a New Reagent for the Gravimetric Determination of Molybdenum(VI)

RAGHUNANDAN SINGH* and R. K. MISHRA

Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur-492 010

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VARIOUS reagents have been recommended for gravimetric determination of molybdenum. Of routine use are α -benzoinoxime¹, 8-hydroxyquinoline² and N-benzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine³. In most of these methods lack of selectivity is often a serious disadvantage. The present paper describes a simple and highly selective method for gravimetric determination of molybdenum and its separation from diverse ions. Though the method does not afford a directly weighable precipitate, yet it can advantageously be applied to selectively estimate molybdenum in pH range 3.0-7.0.

* Author for correspondence; present address: Department of Chemistry, D. B. Science College, Gondia, Maharashtra.